

THE ROLE OF DUOLINGO APP IN LEARNING LANGUAGES: AN ANALYSIS OF EFFECTIVENESS AND USER ENGAGEMENT

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, the effectiveness of the Duolingo app is explored in learning different languages. With the increasing number of language learning apps that are popular tools for self-directed study, it is necessary to pick the most beneficial application. This study offers a more motivational program with everyday notifications and gamification elements, such as rewards, and progress tracking. Additionally, the study highlights the popularity among diverse age groups with the app's accessibility and user-friendly interface. However, limitations were identified, particularly regarding the lack of conversational practice and the absence of some languages in use, such as the Uzbek language. The thesis concludes by discussing other implications and recommendations according to both sides.

Keywords:

Introduction

Globalization and technological advancements foster the improvement of the landscape of language learning. Mobile applications have emerged in this transformation, providing flexible, engaging, accessible ways that allow users to learn at their own pace and on their schedule. Also, social interaction opportunities and diverse learning formats make language learning enjoyable and engaging. If so, which part of the Duolingo program gives more motivation and engagement to learners? During the practice, firstly, Duolingo's colorful design, and enjoyable learning environment appeal to users. Unless people did not have a sense of progress, they would not have preferred this app over other apps. Learners can visibly see their progress as they complete lessons, unlike new lessons, and expand their vocabulary. In short, the combination of gamification, immediate feedback, personalized learning, and a visually appealing interface makes Duolingo highly motivating for many language learners.

Literature review

Technology in language learning

The more advanced and affordable mobile technologies have become in function, the more demand for learning various types of languages has grown in this way in our digital technological era. Being so convenient for learning mobile apps aim to contribute to broadening the educational skills of learning targeting users of all ages, mainly, adults. One of the such handy apps is Duolingo which is a free widely recognized platform that teaches translation coherently, matching clearly, listening repeatedly, and speaking with grammar rules according to units. As of August 15th, 2016, Duolingo has provided wide-ranging languages in its learning materials including: Romanian, Dutch, Russian, Turkish, Spanish, Greek, Arabic, Chinese, Hungarian, Japanese, Ukrainian, English, Indonesian, Thai, and so forth. (Chen, X. 2016)

How does Duolingo work?

In this program, beginners face comprehensive writing tasks and more advanced ones have speaking practice. The app includes a built-in dictionary feature, and games given nearly every aspect of the platform to keep learners engaged while they acquire new vocabulary. For instance, users earn “experience points” (XP) as they complete various learning tasks, like finishing a set lesson. Also, users receive one point for each correct response and lose a point for each mistake, and one unit is considered successful once they accumulate 10 points. Additionally, Duolingo gives feedback to participants and corrects their answers when errors occur during practice, offering helpful tips to improve their language skills. It easily keeps participants continuing by motivating them with congrats.

One of the crucial elements is that Duolingo differs from traditional language programs with its use of gamification. Gamification means making learning fun. Duolingo encourages users to capture materials consistently. The app rewards users for completing lessons, maintaining streaks, and achieving personal milestones. Another good opportunity is that you know your practice ranks among worldwide people. This game-like structure not only enhances motivation but also fosters a sense of accomplishment.

Benefits of Duolingo

Duolingo is the most common way to learn online and it has more than 200million users worldwide. As well as it was created by Luis Won Ahn and Severin Hacker in November 2011. This app offers over 30 online courses for learners who know the English language and the most popular ones include Latin American, Spanish, French, German, Italian, and Brazilian Portuguese.

There are dozens of courses for non-English speaking students. Furthermore, users have the opportunity to suggest other new language courses if they want Duolingo to develop. (Indah Sri Redjeki, R. Muhajir)

Waking of the Covid-19 era has brought transformative changes in the landscape of education, urging educators to try new innovative approaches. In this challenging situation, technology has emerged as a powerful ally and one software has been an attractive solution with its activities and interactive exercises to learn languages. (Jalil Fathi, Mohammad Ahmadne jad, Samireh Nosrati)

Drawbacks of the app

On the authority of Santri Muslima Abila and Ivan Achmad Nurcholis, the software creates a dynamic learning environment consisting of positive and negative sides. They mentioned some disadvantages. Duolingo's dependence on repetition makes people who utilize it boring although a multitude of repetitive tasks can be useful for memorizing. Sentences and phrases are displayed out of context in this mobile app. As a result, comprehending a certain word is a confusing problem for students when they attempt to use certain phrases outside of Duolingo.

According to statistics from 2024, 70% of the users agreed on engagement, and 40% of them were satisfied with the frequency of use. However, the analysis showed a significant drop in motivation that 80% of people confirmed, cultural learning in lessons was only 35% satisfactory that the most users feel Duolingo lacks cultural depth. (Dr. Zia -ur Rehman)

Conclusion

In summary, the Duolingo app has more benefits than drawbacks as a successful learning tool. This app breaks down traditional barriers like wasting time, and not accessing everywhere – available on various devices. There is a daily obligation for learners to inspire with streaks and this well-organized mobile app pays attention to each section of gaining knowledge. Moreover, it receives new participants takes into account their levels and it gives mood with colorful emoji. Another strong point is that app users acquire knowledge of numerous languages at the same time. Duolingo not only makes lessons more entertaining but also develops regular practice, through its gamified approach. Overall, Duolingo represents more valuable advancement among other language learning applications, fostering a love for languages.

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